

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERSONALITY CHARACTERISTICS AND RISKY SEXUAL BEHAVIOURS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN CALABAR METROPOLIS OF CROSS RIVER STATE

EGIM, JOYCE EKPO

**Department of Education Foundation and Childhood Education,
University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria.**

Tel: 08063301505

E-MAIL: joyceegim1978@gmail.com

&

EWA, MOSES APIE, PhD

**Department of Education Foundation and Childhood Education,
University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria**

Tel: 08165596039

Email: moses.ewa@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between personality characteristics and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. With three research questions and three hypotheses formulated to guide the study, correlation research design was adopted in evaluating a sample of two hundred (200) senior secondary school two (SSII) students randomly selected from 23 public schools in the target area during 2022/2023 academic session. Personality Characteristics and Risky Sexual Behaviour Questionnaire (PCRSBQ) was used in data collection. Cronbach Alpha (α) method was used to determine the internal consistency of PCRSBQ and its reliability coefficient was 0.88. Research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the research hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained from the study showed that agreeableness accounted for 38% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis, and that agreeableness significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis; conscientiousness accounted for 35% of variation in risky sexual behaviours and that it significantly relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis; openness to experience accounted for 32% of variation in risky sexual behaviours and that openness to experience significantly relate with risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. It was recommended, among others, that school counsellors should counsel in-school adolescents on the need to explore positive inventions that will help them abstain from sexual misbehaviours.

Introduction

Adolescence brings with it the emergence of sexuality, which presents significant issues for both young individuals and society at large. Adolescents frequently encounter difficulties such as adjusting to the changed structure and functions of a sexually maturing body, overcoming sexual urges and ideals, engaging in sexual behaviour experiments, and assimilating these emotions, perspectives, and experiences into a growing sense of self. The attention associated with being sexually attractive and the unknown excitement of sexual arousal highlight the problem.

The significant effects that teenage sexual behaviour has on the adolescents, their families, and society as a whole make it a social concern. Adolescent sexual behaviour can take many different forms and is not usually associated with sexual contact. For males, nocturnal emission—the outpouring of semen while they sleep—may be an overt sign of sexual maturation. Fewer women engage in the typical practice of masturbation. Adolescent boys and girls are often prone to petting, which carries strong sexual connotations. Teenagers in school typically find petting to be quite enjoyable, arousing, and ego-boosting because it shows acceptance from the other sex. Unfortunately, though, it is sometimes an alluring preamble to sexual activity, for which most teenagers have no plans and frequently swear not to engage.

Any solitary, two-person, or group activity that arouses sexual desire is considered a sexual behaviour. Adolescent sexual behaviour is centered on the sexual experiences, expressions, and behaviours of both males and females. These experiences or behaviours include both sexual and non-sexual interactions such as peripheral and attitude-based behaviours like kissing, petting, and masturbation—the act of stimulating one's sexual organ by caressing it with the hand or mouth. Secondary schools and postsecondary institutions house the majority of young people in our society whose sexual behaviour is cause for considerable concern (Ojong, Akpan, Alasia & Nlumanze, 2014).

Because of the prevalence of hazardous sexual behaviours, there have been many unintended pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and STDs such as HIV. For teenagers enrolled in school, having sex is a high-risk behaviour due to the possible physical and socioemotional risks involved. Although sexual development starts in childhood, sexuality reaches a point throughout adolescence when it becomes so intense that teenagers are forced to pay attention to both themselves and those around them. During this phase, sexual behaviour has particular significance as the teenager begins to consider school socials, after-school events, romantic relationships, dating, and petting. Adolescents' primary physiological causes are essentially increased through

sexual urge brought on by both physical and hormonal changes. Due to peer pressure, social interactions with western cultures, adult model observation, poverty and greed, and peer group dynamics, many of them are exposed to early dating.

The various facets of a person's character that come together to define their personality are what set them apart from other people. It describes the entirety of an individual, including their outward behaviours, looks as well as their distinct pattern of quantifiable, largely stable features. Few researches have examined the influence of personality on middle adolescent sexual development. This study will examine the ways in which personality traits impact sexual behaviours in mid-teenage (15–18 years old), ranging from first physical interactions like kissing to engaging in sexual activity.

According to Asendorpt, Bokenan, Ostendorf and Van-Aken (2001), the three most prevalent personality types across cultures and age groups are resilient (those who lie in the middle), over-controllers (those who have control over their sexuality), and under-controllers (those who can hardly resist or control their sexual urge). Individuals might differ on five personality traits, which make up the Big Five. These characteristics—which go by the names agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to new things, extroversion, neuroticism, or emotional stability—have come to be recognized as a common framework in personality psychology.

Pro-social characteristics, such as a propensity to be empathetic, cordial, and cooperative toward others instead of distrustful and combative, are characterized by agreeableness. Goal-oriented behaviour and impulse control are characterized by conscientiousness, which also refers to the desire to be orderly, dependable, self-disciplined, act obediently, aim for achievement, and favour planned behaviour over spontaneous behaviour. A person's level of intellectual curiosity, enjoyment of art, emotion, adventure, novel concepts, and diversity of experiences are all reflected in their openness to new experiences. It also characterizes how complicated their mental and experimental life is. Outgoing, vivacious, happy feelings, assertiveness, friendliness, a propensity to seek stimulation in other people's company, and talkativeness are characteristics of extroversion. A person's mood is characterized by their neuroticism or emotional stability, which is defined as their propensity to feel negative emotions like vulnerability, anger, anxiety, and despair frequently.

Adolescents who lack self-control tend to exhibit low levels of conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness to new experiences. They also tend to exhibit high levels of extroversion and average levels of neuroticism or emotional stability. Adolescents who exhibit overcontrol exhibit a high degree of agreeableness, conscientiousness,

extroversion, openness to new experiences, and a low degree of neuroticism or emotional stability. The researchers conducted this study to determine whether personality traits have any bearing on sexual behaviours among secondary school students in the Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. The study was motivated by the ongoing rise in the number of teenagers living with HIV/AIDS, STIs, and teenage pregnancies.

Statement of the Problem

In actuality, sex is intended to be enjoyed inside the framework of marriage. The sexual behaviour of adolescents is concerning, particularly in the majority of secondary schools located in the Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. The prevalence of teenage pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and STDs among our youth has drawn the attention of policymakers, educators, counselors, religious authorities, parents, and concerned individuals. Adolescents engagement in premarital sexual behaviours has an impact on society as a whole as well as their parents. Due to their high sexual urge, many teenagers in school resort to prostitution, numerous sex relationships, hazardous sex, and premarital sex. There is a global trend toward a reducing average age of menarche, a declining age of first sexual debut, a rise in the number of sexually active teenagers, and a decline in high-risk sexual behaviours among teenagers.

Concerned about the rising prevalence of teenage premarital sex and the ensuing fallout, the government has passed legislation outlawing prostitution. Furthermore, school administrators have made a number of attempts to curtail these kinds of sexual behaviours. Teens who become involved and the school administration finds out about it fear suspension or even expulsion, particularly if a pregnancy is confirmed. Based on the researchers' experience, a large number of teenagers continue to engage in premarital sexual behaviours. The alarming aspect of this issue is how frequently kids and teenagers engage in this behaviour and the ensuing harm it causes to them, their parents, and society at large. The goal of the study was to provide potential remedies to reduce young people's engagement in dangerous sexual behaviours.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between personality characteristics and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the relationship between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.
2. Assess the relationship between conscientiousness and risky sexual behaviours

among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

3. Ascertain the relationship between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. How does agreeableness relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?
2. How does conscientiousness relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?
3. How does openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised for the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.
2. Conscientiousness does not significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.
3. There is no significant relationship between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Method

The design adopted for this study is correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all the senior secondary school two (SS II) students in the 23 public secondary schools in both Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Area during the 2022/2023 academic session, totalling 3,401 (2,219 from Calabar Municipality and 1,182 from Calabar South) out of which 1,338 were males and 2,063 were females. The sample of the study comprised 200 SS II students randomly drawn from seven public secondary schools in Calabar Metropolis. The sampling technique adopted in this study was stratified random sampling technique. The reason was to give the schools equal opportunities for selection. The researchers stratified the schools into two based on Local Education Authorities and then selected the schools in each stratum through simple random technique. In this regard, the researchers selected 30% of the schools from each of the strata for the study, indicating that five schools were selected from Calabar Municipality and two schools from Calabar South through simple random sampling. In the same manner, the researchers randomly drew 20% of the students in each of the selected schools

making it a total of 200 SS II students out of which 136 of the students were from Calabar Municipality and 64 students from Calabar South for the study.

Data were collected using the “Personality Characteristics and Risky Sexual Behaviour Questionnaire (PCRSBQ)”. The questionnaire was divided into three sections: A, B and C. Section A elicited information about personal data of the subjects such as sex and age; Section B was a modified four point Likert type scale of thirty (30) items questionnaire which sought to elicit response about personality characteristics of the respondents; Section C consisted of ten items that measured the students' risky sexual behaviours on a modified four point Likert type scale.

The validity of the instrument was determined by two Psychologists and one Measurement and Evaluation expert in the Department. Their comments and suggestions were applied appropriately to improve the quality of the instrument. PCRSBQ was administered to 30 students randomly selected from two public secondary schools in Akpabuyo Local Government Area who were not part of the sample but share similar characteristics with those in Calabar Metropolis. The data collected from the PCRSBQ were scored and analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method which gave an overall reliability coefficient of 0.88.

Data collection was done in the sampled schools. The researchers first visited the sampled schools to familiarize with the school authority and explained the purpose of the study after which they administered the questionnaire to the respondents. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviations. The mean value of 2.50 was used as a benchmark for decision, while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance

Results

Research Question One

How does agreeableness relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on how agreeableness relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students

N = 200				
S/N	Item Statement	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Dec.
1	I always find fault in what others do.	3.02	0.81	A
2	I have always tried to be helpful to others.	3.00	1.03	A
3	Whenever I have a disagreement with someone, I am always the one that started the quarrel.	3.03	0.78	A
4	I always find it very difficult to forgive people who wrong me.	2.33	0.76	D
5	I usually trust all the people I meet.	2.13	0.90	D

Dec = decision, A = agreed, D = disagreed

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviations of respondents on how agreeableness relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result obtained shows that items 1, 2 and 3 had mean ratings of 3.02, 3.00 and 3.03 with standard deviations of 0.81, 1.03 and 0.78, respectively. These mean values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 which implies “agreed” to the following responses on how agreeableness relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis: I always find fault in what others do, I have always tried to be helpful to others, and whenever I have a disagreement with someone, I am always the one that start the quarrel. However, 'I always find it very difficult to forgive people who wrong me', and 'I usually trust all the people I meet' are “disagreed” because their mean values are less than 2.50

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) Analysis of the Relationship between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students

Variables	N	R	R ²	P-Value	Dec
Agreeableness	200	0.62	0.38	0.03	S
Risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students	200				

Pearson Product Moment Correlation = R, R² = Coefficient of determination, P-value = Probability value, Dec. = Decision

Table 2 shows that the correlation between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis was 0.62. This shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among them. The coefficient of determination 0.38 which is also known as the predictive value means that agreeableness accounted for 38% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. A probability value of 0.03 was obtained. Since the probability value of 0.03 is less than 0.05 set as level of significance ($P < 0.05$), this means that the result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between agreeableness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is rejected, meaning that agreeableness significantly relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Research Question Two

How does conscientiousness relate with risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on how does conscientiousness relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students

N = 200				
S/N	Item Statement	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Dec
6	I can be careless most times.	2.71	0.72	A
7	When people rely on me, it is because I do things well.	2.59	0.80	A
8	I am not always disorganized.	2.77	0.84	A
9	I always persevere until the task have finished.	2.85	0.91	A
10	I always make plans and follow them until I succeed.	3.00	0.86	A

Dec = decision, A = agreed, D = disagreed

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviations of respondents on how conscientiousness relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result obtained shows that items 6-10 had mean ratings of 2.71, 2.59, 2.77, 2.85, and 3.00 with standard deviations of 0.72, 0.80, 0.84, 0.91 and 0.86, respectively. These mean values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 which implies agreed.

Hypothesis Two

Conscientiousness does not significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) Analysis of the Relationship between conscientiousness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students

Variables	N	R	R ²	P-Value	Dec
Conscientiousness	200				
Risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students	200	0.59	0.35	0.01	S

Pearson Product Moment Correlation = R, R² = Coefficient of determination, P-value = Probability value, Dec. = Decision

Table 4 shows that the correlation between conscientiousness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students was 0.59. This shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between conscientiousness and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students. The coefficient of determination 0.35 which is also known as the predictive value means that conscientiousness accounted for 35% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students. A probability value of 0.01 was obtained. Since the probability value of 0.01 is less than 0.05 set as level of significance ($P < 0.05$), this means that the result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that conscientiousness does not significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that conscientiousness significantly relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Research Question Three

How does openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on how openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students

N = 200				
S/N	Item Statement	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Dec.
11	I am always original when it comes to new ideas.	3.02	1.01	A
12	Most times I am curious about many different things.	3.04	0.91	A
13	I always see myself having an active imagination.	2.43	0.69	D
14	I always prefer work that is routine.	2.41	0.82	D
15	I don't like reflecting on ideas at all.	2.38	0.81	D

Dec = decision, A = agreed, D = disagreed

Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviations of respondents on how openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result obtained shows that items 1 and 2 had mean ratings of 3.02 and 3.04 with standard deviations of 1.01 and 0.91, respectively. These mean values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 which implies agreed. This means the following responses on how openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis are agreed. These include: 'I am always original when it comes to new ideas', and 'most times, I am curious about many different things'. However, 'I always see myself having an active imagination', 'I always prefer work that is routine', and 'I don't like reflecting on ideas at all' are disagreed because their mean values are less than 2.50.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) Analysis of the Relationship between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students

Variables	N	R	R ²	P-Value	Dec
Openness to experience	200				
Risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students	200	0.57	0.32	0.01	S

Pearson Product Moment Correlation = R, R² = Coefficient of determination, P-value = Probability value, Dec. = Decision

Table 6 shows that the correlation between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis was 0.57. This shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The coefficient of determination 0.32 which is also known as the predictive value means that openness to experience accounted for 32% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. A probability value of 0.01 was obtained. Since the probability value of 0.01 is less than 0.05 set as level of significance ($P < 0.05$), this means that the result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between openness to experience and risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis is rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that openness to experience significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

Agreeableness and Risky Sexual Behaviours among Secondary School Students

The result obtained from table 1 showed how agreeableness relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar. The result in table 2 showed that agreeableness accounted for 38% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis, and that agreeableness significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. This result does not concur with the findings of Ibigbami, Adewuya, Akinsulore, Aloba, Mapayi, Ibigbami and Olowookere (2019). The study revealed that agreeableness had significant negative correlations with risky sexual behaviours. The finding is also in disagreement with the study by Allen and Walter (2018) who found out that agreeableness had significant negative relationship with sexually aggressive behaviours and sexual infidelity.

Conscientiousness and Risky Sexual Behaviours among Secondary School Students

The result obtained from table 3 showed how conscientiousness relates with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result in table 4 showed that conscientiousness accounted for 35% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students, and that conscientiousness significantly relate with risky sexual behaviours. This result disagrees with the findings of Ibigbami, Adewuya, Akinsulore, Aloba, Mapayi, Ibigbami and Olowookere (2019) who found that conscientiousness had significant negative correlations with risky sexual behaviours. However, the finding agrees with

the study by Firoozi, Azmoude and Asgharipoor (2016) who found a significant relationship between conscientiousness and sexual self-esteem.

Openness to experience and Risky Sexual Behaviours among Secondary School Students

The result obtained from table 5 showed how openness to experience relate with risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis. The result in table 6 showed that openness to experience accounted for 32% of variation in risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Calabar Metropolis, and that openness to experience significantly relate with risky sexual behaviour. This result is not in concord with the findings of Morales, Méndez, Orgilés and Espada (2016) as they found weak but significant link between sexual risk and personality facets. However, the finding is in accordance with the study by Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje (2014). The authors found that personality traits (agreeableness, neuroticism, openness to experience, extraversion and conscientiousness) had a significant influence on violent behaviours among adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. The school counsellors should counsel in-school adolescents on the need to explore positive inventions that will help them abstain from sexual misbehaviours.
2. There is need to focus attention on psychological factors in environmental and health care management.
3. Parents should encourage their children to be focused and goal oriented so as to discipline themselves against risky sexual behaviours.
4. The school counsellors should also counsel the students to realise that being soft-hearted or lenient is not a yardstick to give oneself cheaply to premarital sexual behaviours.
5. The school authorities should make sure that adolescents' enthusiasm is not geared towards sexual misbehaviours but academic prowess.

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